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Psychospiritual Perspectives on the Other

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Abstract: Social sciences' and theological understandings of the "other" or the *anawim* have moved beyond traditional and conservative understandings. Understandings differ according to academic disciplines and thus there are various definitions, approaches and ways of knowing the "other." The *anawim* in today's literature include immigrants, the homeless, Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans and Queer (LGBTQ), and the elderly. Issues of domination, discrimination and exclusivity arise when considering them, in opposition to values of equality, unity and inclusivity. This article discusses two of the *anawim* - the "missing" girl child and the elderly. The "missing" girl child is a person with rights right from the moment of conception. The elderly are considered in terms of quality of life, isolation and meaning making. Psychospiritual dimensions are touched upon and a theology of action explicated.

Keywords: The other, domination, discrimination, girl child, elderly

When we consider "the other," it means there is a difference; either two persons or two groups. It could be a majority group, minority or smaller groups, groups with more voice, money, power and those with less. The understanding of "the other" has been studied across various scientific disciplines including, anthropology, sociology, psychology, neuroscience, medicine, and theology. All these disciplines have their definitions, approaches and understandings. In considering groups as separate, elements of domination,

discrimination and exclusivity arise, in opposition to values of equality, unity and inclusivity. Noort and Noort (2012) give us an understanding of the relationship between the “I” and “the other.” They state: “Our uniqueness, defines our personal and social identity. But it is in the social relation that the “other” defines me, and “I” define the “other.” By recognizing difference and setting boundaries we construct the identity both of the other as well as ourselves” (p. 503)

Social sciences’ expanded understanding notwithstanding; theological understandings of the “I” and “the other” too have crossed borders. Scientific and empirical research has expanded this understanding by going beyond traditional and conservative understandings. Also, the human personality is dynamic, constantly evolving, whether emotionally, physically, mentally, or spiritually. Religious and spiritual affiliations define a lot of who the person is and how a human functions in the world. In a world where more and more people are making choices of their form of religion and spirituality, these understandings are being expanded and explored.

In the Christian understanding, a term for the “other” would be the *anawim*. The *anawim*, are many, and include women (Lk 8:1-3, NRSV), children (Lk 18: 15-17, NRSV), widows (Mk 12:41-44, NRSV), the poor (Lk 13:10-17, NRSV), the Samaritan (Jn 4:1-45, NRSV), the gentiles (Mt 4: 15, NRSV), and orphans (Jas 1: 27, NRSV). In today’s world, with a broader understanding of the context, we add immigrants (Esses, Medianu, Hamilton, & Lapshina, 2015), homeless (Ahmed, Chaudhry, Afzal, Farooq, 2015), LGBTQ (Johnson, Amella, 2014), persons with disability (Swinton, 2011), and the elderly (Das, 2011). This presentation is in light of the expanding understandings of the “I” and “the other,” utilizing biblical understandings of *anawim*, in the light of scientific research and “sensitivity” (“Pope Francis,” 2013). This is so that the *anawim* might have a clearer voice, face less

discrimination and have an equal status, in a multicultural and diverse world.

1. Multiculturalism and Diversity

Some issues of multiculturalism and diversity are not easily spoken about in mainstream society. Most considerations take place with the majority in mind. Whether it be human right abuses, marginalization, or biases with regard to skin color, caste groups, age or economic backgrounds; the majority, the dominant, powerful, those with voice, men become the bases for examining these issues. These issues need to be addressed not only to build awareness but also from the point of societal integration.

In India gender-based violence is one such issue. It includes foeticide, rapes, honor killings and sexual abuse. These have taken on insidious forms that are justified in the name of faith, community, even development. Intolerance of other faiths, through attacks on places of worship is significantly on the rise. The target groups include Christians, and Muslims who are among the religious minorities in India. People of alternate sexuality too are prone to violence in a society not open to persons of diverse sexualities and orientations. Similarly, there is a profound shift in the understanding of what is happening to older Indians—in the context of changing family relationships, values and severely limited old-age income support.

This article examines some questions that arise out of these now common issues in society. This article is restricted to two of “the other”- the ‘missing’ girl child, and the elderly. Psychospiritual dimensions are touched upon. The questions considered are (1) Who is the “other” for us today? (b) What is the understanding of the “other?” (c) How can “the other” be understood and integrated better in society today? These questions are examined, and a theology of action explicated.

2. The ‘Missing’ Girl Child

This section is on the unborn child, or the newborn child. It situates the violence done to women, not just from the time the girl child is born, but while even in the womb. Rights of the unborn are trampled upon; they have no voice. Giving voice to the voiceless, to those who are not even born, is something that is not considered in a country, where value is placed on the male child. Patriarchal religious traditions celebrate girls as young wives and mothers, not as the girls they are and is a key component of girls’ disempowerment (Stith, 2015). There is a triple injustice here - to the unborn, the girl child, and to the voiceless.

Globally an estimated 100 million women have been eliminated from population statistics (Stith, 2015). Survival chances of girls in parts of south and East Asia have been adverse. Female feticide, infanticide, abandonment, under-reporting of female births, and selective neglect of girls leading to higher death rates have contributed to this adversity. Female feticide has increased by 49.2% in India between 1999-2000, (“National Crime Records Bureau”) especially in the north and north western parts of India (Dey, Nambiar, Lakshmi, Sheikh, & Reddy, 2003). The United Nations Children’s Fund, estimated that upto 50 million girls and women are ‘missing’ from India’s population because of termination of the female fetus or high mortality of the girl child due to lack of proper care and that as many as 10 million female fetuses were aborted in India over the past two decades (Chunga, & Das, 2011). Punjab epitomizes the growing phenomenon of feticide, and sex-selective abortion of girls (Sarkaria, 2009). In India, the most plausible explanation for fewer female than male births seems to be prenatal sex determination (Sahni, Verma, Narula, Varghese, Sreenivas, & Puliyeel, 2008) followed by induced abortion of female fetuses. The differences in sex ratios between slum and elite areas is also significant (Bhardwaj,

Nagargoje, Jadhao, & Khadse, 2011). The question that arises is how to give voice to those who cannot speak.

Much has been written about the girl child in scriptures. In the Old Testament, this discrimination, domination and inequality is evident. We see an apparent preferential option given to the girl child in Exodus 1: 16, which is not really a preferential option, as the Egyptians did not want Hebrew male children, and so would kill them. They let the girl child live, as girls and women, were not considered of any importance then. We do hear the prophet Zechariah express positivity when he says “The city streets will be filled with boys and girls playing there (Zech 8:5, NRSV).” The Old Testament also presents a strong woman like Naomi, who put the welfare of her daughters-in-law ahead of her own and Ruth her daughter-in-law, who stood by her (Ruth1:16, NIV). There are also examples of strong wives like Sarah (Gen 21:26), Rachel and Leah (Gen 21:26).

More and more equality and concern is brought in by Jesus, and his option for the *anawin* is seen when he raises the dead girl (Mat 9:18, NRSV). That women had a voice and spoke directly with men and even confronted them is seen in Mt 26: 69, and Mat 26:71, when Peter was confronted by the servant girls. The role of the Marys’ and other women in the New Testament, cannot be underestimated e.g. Mary the mother of Jesus (Acts 1:14, NRSV), Mary of Magdalena (Mk 16:1, NRSV), and Mary the sister of Lazarus (Jn 11:1, NRSV). Jesus did not reduce women to the background, he portrayed them as strong. Similarities and dissimilarities notwithstanding, power needs to be given to the *anawim*, for a more real status in a world that Jesus conceived.

We as Christians need to remove any boundaries that have been created through patriarchal structures, and bring in thinking more in line with Jesus’ way of living. That is important for a healthy spiritual health and development.

We also need to recognize that men and women understand and express their love for God differently (Hoffman, Knight, Boscoe-Huffman, & Stewart, 2008), and that elements of superiority and inferiority are present. Experientially, females perceive God as loving and caring, and men as a God who is dominating and controlling (Hoffman, Knight, Boscoe-Huffman, & Stewart, 2008).

Jesus went beyond cultural, ethnic and gender barriers. He did not treat anyone based on what others say, their accomplishments, possessions, or appearance. For Jesus, gender was irrelevant in his offer of salvation. In terms of spiritual authority all God's people are equal (Stith, 2015). Society in general, and some Indian states in particular, need to learn to value the girl child so that we do not have any more 'missing' girl children. They need to acknowledge that the girl child is a full person with rights, from the moment of conception. She is a child of God, part of his kingdom of love, peace and hope.

3. The Elderly

The size of the elderly population is increasing over time. By 2050 there will be almost 2 billion people over 60, around 22% of the forecasted total world population (Flynn, 2009). In India from 5.6% in 1961 it is projected to rise to 12.4% of population by the year 2026. The problems and issues of its grey population have not been given serious consideration (Das, 2011), although the government has come out with a number of acts and policies with regard to the aging population. One of them is "The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007" which provides for,

maintenance of Parents/ senior citizens by children/ relatives made obligatory and justiciable through Tribunals, revocation of transfer of property by senior citizens in case of negligence by relatives, penal provision for abandonment of senior citizens, establishment of Old

Age Homes for Indigent Senior Citizens, and adequate medical facilities and security for Senior Citizens.

Also, the National Policy on Older Persons (NPOP), 1999, envisages “state support to ensure financial and food security, health care, shelter and other needs of older persons, equitable share in development, protection against abuse and exploitation, and availability of services to improve the quality of their lives.” These two acts and policies among the many others address some of the problems that confront the elderly in India, today. They set the tone for what the government is doing; the rest needs to be done at the grassroots level. A significant consideration is the mental health of older adults.

Ignorance, loneliness, negligence and social isolation in older adults are major problems these days (Ahmed, Chaudhry, Afzal, & Farooq, 2015). Transitions can significantly affect quality of life. Participation in some sort of activity is crucial for psychosocial health and well-being as they help improve life satisfaction, social isolation, and loneliness. This results in greater life satisfaction and lower levels of social isolation. Forming alliances and group identities is the key for building new relationships and maintaining relationships in the community (Winstead, Yost, Cotton, Berkowsky, & Anderson, 2014). There is a need to identify the positive aspects of growing old and what is gained during this time period rather than what is lost. This is necessary to avoid disease, maintain high cognitive and physical function, and active engagement with life (Aldwin, & Igarashi, 2015). This would result in an improved quality of life (Winstead, Yost, Cotten, Berkowsky, & Anderson, 2014).

The Old and New Testaments are quite clear about the roles of the elderly in society and family. They talk about the need for the elderly, the needs of the elderly and of fertility (Gen 5:32; 21:5, NRSV) of the elderly. That respect has to be given to the elderly, is clearly stated in Lev 19:32 and that a long

life brings understanding (Job 12:12, NRSV). In the book of Proverbs, we read that children's children are a crown to the aged, and that parents are the pride of their children (Prov 17:6, NRSV). The difficulties and infirmities of the elderly are addressed in Matthew 8:17. The role that the elderly played in the early Church is emphasized and thus their importance, as is heard in the letter to James (5:14-16, NRSV):

Is anyone among you sick? Let them call the elders of the church to pray over them and anoint them with oil in the name of the Lord. And the prayer offered in faith will make the sick person well; the Lord will raise them up. If they have sinned, they will be forgiven. Therefore, confess your sins to each other and pray for each other so that you may be healed. The prayer of a righteous person is powerful and effective.

4. Discussion

When considering the “other” it is necessary to reflect on “who is the other is for me?” It makes us consider the relationship between the “I” and the “other.” This is related to the question, “who is the God we worship?” The answer is revealed to us through the life, death and resurrection of Jesus Christ (Swinton, 2011) and in this revelation from Him, we realize his options. Having thus considered this relationship, we check for prejudicial understandings, considerations that need to be worked at, or understandings that have changed, with regard to the ‘missing’ girl child and the elderly. It implies an explicit and implicit response to include the “other” into the very fabric of society; not as an afterthought, but fully.

An acknowledgement of prejudices is necessary in order to respond after reflection. With regard to the ‘missing’ girl child and the elderly, it brings up the need for giving voice to the voiceless, power, dependencies and the absence of equality. If Jesus came for all peoples, then it must be Society, including Christian society that imposes conditions, sets in barriers,

so that groups get separated from each other. Differences exist and although it is not necessary to agree with another's worldview, it is important to recognize the tension between different world views and belief systems and the imposition of one on the other (Hoffman, Knight, Boscoe-Huffman, & Stewart, 2008). This occurs only through the creation of equal structures and the realization that openness works better than self-centeredness. Thus issues of equality (as opposed to discrimination), unity (as opposed to domination) and inclusivity (as opposed to exclusivity) need to be addressed.

a. Women

The role of women in history has been constructed and reconstructed. At one time it was thought that women were originally for the purpose of reproduction and survival of the species. Later on other aspects of relationships and intimacy also began to be considered. This process has been paralleled in the Catholic Church's understanding. At times during the history of Christianity, sex was considered to be solely for reproductive purposes. The church has now placed sex in the context of a broader relational understanding. For married couples, sex is now understood to be, part of a healthy intimate relationship and enhances mental health. It is only when one affirms that women are an essential part of society, not just sex objects or objects for procreation, will their full worth in society be realized, and the killings of the girl child stopped.

The critical areas of concern are the human rights of women, specifically the girl child. This has been spoken of globally at the UN as well as nationally, to ensure equality and non-discrimination under the law and in practice. The drop in the sex ratio of girls in India, in the 0-6 age group from 945 in 1991 to 927 in 2001, indicates that the preference of society is sons. This means that parents and their partners are actively involved in not allowing the girl child to be born, especially in certain communities in India. There are very specific laws

framed to prevent such crimes. Some of the laws are: crime against children – murder (“Indian Penal Code” Section 302), infanticide (“Indian Penal Code” Section 315), and feticide (“Indian Penal Code” Section 315, 316). In considering the ‘missing’ girl child, women, advocates, families, health professionals and researchers need to rethink and improve existing protocols and interventions for children (Bonilla, 2005). Protective measure like the pre-natal diagnostic techniques act (PCPNDT), 1994 and the medical termination of pregnancy act (MTP), 1971, should be strictly implemented with regard to their regulation and prevention of misuse.

b. The Elderly

Successful aging is meaning related. It involves self-acceptance, self-contentment and engagement with life. Self-acceptance includes “realistic self-appraisal, a review of one’s life, and focusing on the present, and engagement with life including openness to experience, generativity, social interactions, and positivity” (Aldwin, & Igarashi, 2015). Although healthy individuals would be more likely to participate in community activities, even those who believe that they are less healthy have greater life satisfaction when they do participate. This is what Pope John Paul II in his address to the 2nd World Assembly on Aging, 3 April, 2002, said:

The elderly should never be considered a burden on society, but a resource which can contribute to society’s well-being. Not only do they show that there are aspects of life—human, cultural, moral and social values—which cannot be judged in terms of economic efficiency, but they can also make an effective contribution in the work-place and in leadership roles. In short, it is not just a question of doing something for older people, but also of accepting them in a realistic way as partners in shared projects—at the level of thought, dialogue and action.

With the elderly population increasing it is important that their maintenance and welfare be considered. The health care, shelter and other needs of older persons need to be looked after so that they have an equitable share in development, protection against abuse and exploitation. Services to improve the quality of their lives might have to include care of the elderly by children and relatives under pain of the law. Property transfers might have to be revoked in case of negligence, and abandonment should result in penal provisions. These areas of concern are necessary so that financial and food security of the elderly are ensured. For the aged, interventions to promote optimal aging, cognizant of the characteristics of the target audience must be considered. Life review, wisdom enhancement, and mindfulness-based interventions may be effective in promoting greater well-being. A combination of therapies that include wisdom enhancement therapy should be developed for application (Aldwin, & Igarashi, 2015). Spirituality, and other spiritually related coping strategies should be considered for those with relevant spiritual and religious concerns along with the resources that spirituality may offer.

5. Conclusion

Minority groups offer opportunities to challenge theological and political perspectives and actions that cause pain and distress (El-Khoury, Dutton, Goodman, Engel, Belamaric, & Murphy, 2004). The bible clearly states that God sent his only son for “all peoples” to complete his work, and the work of Gods people is, “to believe in the one he has sent.” This belief implies, that Jesus came for all kinds of people, children, (Lk 19: 15-17, NRSV) the poor, and the Samaritan (Jn 4: 1- 45, NRSV), the girl child, the elderly and that all groups and peoples have access to him. There are many *anawim* today. These oppressed groups welcome interaction with those with greater voice, money and who are dominant. Interaction,

dialogue, and listening are essential starting points for attitudinal changes. They help in breaking down subtleties of behavior, action and thought.

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